

The Phenomenon of Ethnic Minorities' Nationalism in Nigeria with Special Focus on the Niger Delta Peoples

By

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Abstract

The restructure or amalgamation in 1914 witnessed largely the bringing together of two Nigeria's notably the Northern and Southern Protectorates. This was followed by further balkanization into three regions of North, West and East respectively in 1939, to basically quench the nationalists' agitation to be included in the legislative process, the Richard's Constitution of 1946 was introduced, bringing the whole of Nigeria into a single legislative agenda. The irony of this development the paper contend is that, it breeds and cross-fertilized cultural groupings that later metamorphosed into political parties with a phenomenon referred to as ethnic majority and minority groups, in the various regions. It is therefore the argument that, the nationalists were fighting for the liberation and ascendancy of the majority ethnic groups at the expense of the minorities, that gave rise to the cut-throat competition among ethnically formed parties with the pretension of fighting for the emancipation of Nigeria. This exercise was well perfected by the Lyttleton Constitution of 1954 built on the regionalism principle that made the regional assemblies autonomous as well as their characterization of federating units. This episode, however, fanned the embers of ethnic nationalism, and became the turning point in the history of ethnic minorities' generally and the Niger Delta peoples in particular. It was believed there existed some form of homogeneity in the regions. However, using the historical analysis approach to x – ray the findings shows that, the aggressive promotion of ethnic nationalism on the part of the ethnic majors and their ethnically based parties was the contradiction that made the minorities' to recognized that their interests were not taken into account of the regions in which they were compressed into. And the expression of this fear of their being subsumed culturally and politically within the regional structure climaxed the calls for separate regions or states, among others for survival has marked this process in contemporary vocabulary as minorities' ethnic nationalism in Nigeria's spectrum.

Keywords: Nationalism, Ethnicity, Ethnic Nationalism, Majority, Minority and Niger Delta

Introduction

The Niger Delta is a geo-ecological region in the Southern part of Nigeria that protrude into the Gulf of Guinea, which is an arm of the Atlantic Ocean. This geographic region covers about 480kms of the Nigerian coastline flanked by the Benin River in the West to the Cross River Estuary in the East and its adjoining

hinterland. This is majorly where the River Niger and its tributaries empty their waters into the Atlantic Ocean. The region spreads across five ecological zones namely; low land rain forest, the montane, derived savannah, fresh water swamp and mangrove forest (Ibaba, 2017:6). The topography of the region is about two metres above sea level (Singh, Moffat & Linden 1995: 8). The area is flat, rain fall is high, consequently, it is Africa's largest delta as such, water takes about 2,370 square Km of its land mass (cited in Ibaba, 2017: Ibid).

This complex physiographic areas has evoked two broad categories in the historiography, one that defines it as a geographic entity and the other which sees it an oil producing region. Whereas the geographic description comprises six states of Akwa-Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Rivers as the composition of the region, Abia, Imo and Ondo states are included in the conception of the Niger Delta as oil producing region. While conceptualizing the Niger Delta Professor Tekena Tamuno asserts that this new coinage widely described as the political definition of the Niger Delta is the accepted definition in policy cycles (Tamuno, 2000:11-12), the six states structure define by geographic consideration defines the Niger Delta in this paper. However Etekpe says that the six states structure of the Niger Delta is basically derived from the Niger Delta Development Board Act of 1960 while the NDDC Act of 2007 expanded its scope to become nine (Etekpe, 2007).

Given this multiple strands, the concept of Niger Delta become suggestive of different thing to many people, subsuming as it where even the historical or cartographic definition of sort. Arguing on the multiple scope and usage Ibaba contends that with state creation, boundary adjustments and oil politics some Niger Delta communities may be located within states outside the widely accepted six Niger Delta States, just as non-Niger Delta communities may be in the area for same reason (Ibaba, 2005).

Over 28 million Nigerians according to UNDP live in the Niger Delta (UNDP 2006:25). It comprises of about 20 ethnic minority groups, 800 communities (Okoko & Ibaba, 1997:57), and UNDP also reported that 7,717 settlements there are in the Niger Delta (UNDP, 2006:23). The diverse minority groups in the region have lived there for many millennia, especially the predominant ethnic group, the Ijo for over 7,000 years (Alagoa, 2004:1). Other ethnic nationalities in the Niger Delta include the Itsekiri, Urhobo, Isoko, Efik, Ibiobio, Annang, Ikwere, Etche, Ogoni, Ndokwa, Ika Ibo, among others.

The Niger Delta and its peoples had shared in the benefits that occasioned from the white man's high and elevated status, and material benefits. It was also the center from which European influence such as Christianity, trade etc. extended to many

Nigerian groups especially the Igbo, which Professor Dike correctly described as “the frontier of opportunity” (Dike, 1956:30). Following the firm establishment of colonialism and its policies in the hinterland (especially Igbo land) caused conflict due largely from ethnic prejudices of domination of the Niger Delta peoples of the meagre resources, and especially the scarcity of jobs for the educated elites which are only made available in places where colonial governments are seated. Arising from the above scenario, all gravitated to these urban centers to compete for jobs, which were been discriminated. This is aptly captured as Schwarz (1968) argued that, the rivalry of these nations is as bitter as the struggles between Jews and Arabs in Palestine. While the Palestine argument is largely over land, the Nigerian one is over jobs, contracts, scholarship and the rights of traders to establishment themselves outside their region of origin.

It is instructive to also note that, in the early days of the colonial enterprise the Niger Delta peoples monopolized the junior officers’ cadre of the colonial service even to the early 1930s. Subsequently the Igbos had produced their own educated elites as Eferibo forcefully argues who now look upon these positions in their ethnic quarters as rightly theirs. He further contends pressure was mounted on the colonial administration as many of the Niger Delta occupants of these positions lost their jobs on account of this to the Igbo in the Mid 1930s on the one hand. While on the other hand, the swift movement of Igbos across the ethnic frontiers during the colonial period, especially as emigrant traders began invading the economic “holy of holies” of the Niger Delta competed as fishermen and fish traders in the 1940s were prone to discrimination and conflict among these ethnically different peoples injected ethnic prejudice (Eferibo 2013:255-256).

Arguably therefore, the introduction of political activities in colonial Nigeria in 1922, and further re-organization of the colonial enterprise in 1941 and 1946 when the British Government created the first 25 provinces and further decided to regroup the provinces into three region for administrative convenience, the Niger Delta was balkanize into two regions, Western and Eastern Region. The aforementioned background issues coupled with the ecological, historical, cultural as well as the fear of domination by the ethnic majority groups provided the incendiary for the South-South (Niger Delta) peoples to galvanize and agitated for separate province/state such as Calabar-Ogoja-Rivers (COR), Rivers states etc. as elsewhere in colonial Nigeria preparatory to flag independence in 1960. This thought process led to the formation of many socio-cultural organizations by the minority elements in the Eastern Region for direction since the 1940s. The idea started especially among the Ijo, and was later welcomed by other related groups who suffered same in the hands

of the majority groups. Thus, Ijo Rivers Peoples League, Rivers Chiefs and Peoples Conference, Ibibio Unions, Ogoni Divisional Union etc, are just few examples to be mentioned, that vigorously struggled for the survival of the Niger Delta minorities up to 1967, when Rivers and South Eastern (Cross River) States were excised from the Eastern Region. The point to be made here is that, this struggle for their survival still continues in the contemporary time was characterized by both separatist and statist is what has been referred to as ethnic minorities' nationalism in Nigeria.

This paper will attempt to highlight some of the features of ethnic minorities struggle in Nigeria within the confines of its genesis, struggle for creation of states, struggle for derivation, and armed struggle, in conformity with the Niger Delta minorities' nationalism.

There are many concepts tied to this paper that would require clarification for ease of understanding. These are nationalism, ethnicity, ethnic nationalism, minority and majority. The clarification of these concepts have been extensively documented by many scholarly studies especially Okwudiba Nnoli (1978) is too well known to require further reconsideration here.

Struggle for Creation of States

The establishment of three regions of north, west and east from 1939 to 1954 created two categories of groups majority and minority resulted in the grouping of the ethnic minority groups such as the Igala, Tiv, Kanuri, Jukun in the north, the Ijo, Urhobo, Itsekiri, Edo, Isoko and the western Igbo in the west, the Efik, Annang, Ibibio, Ogoja, Ikwere, Ijo in the east with the more populous and dominant groups: the Hausa in the north, the Yoruba in the west and the Igbo in the east. Though federalism had been introduced to tackle ethnic nationalism, rather it created the basis for heighten mutual suspicion and antagonism. It consequently gave rise to the emergence of minority political movements. Fearing political domination and socio-economic discrimination under the tripartite regional arrangement, the ethnic minorities' campaign vigorously for the creation of additional states in which their minority status would substantially ameliorated or totally minimized (Suberu, 1999:16). It was this uncanny truth that propelled the minorities especially the Niger Delta nationalities to join forces to press for a state rather than to split them between the Eastern and Western Regions under the Igbo and Yoruba.

The Niger Delta minorities had severally argued that the regionalization system based at Enugu and Ibadan were too remote from them; worst still, did not understand their peculiar ecological and developmental challenges, and therefore demanded a separate state or province with its capital in the Niger Delta. They wanted this actualized before the attainment of independence. The aforementioned

above propelled Chief Harold Dappa Biriye to fight for the creation of a Rivers Province which they hoped, would not only bring government apparatus to their door steps, but would also accelerate the process to redress the long years of neglect. At about the same time, according to Professor Ben Naanen that, similar agitations were also being galvanized among non-Ijo Rivers people. The agitation climaxed with the creation of the Rivers Province in 1947, comprising Ahoada, Brass, Degema, and Ogoni with Port Harcourt as its headquarters (Naanen, 2002:341). It is therefore clear from the above submission that the provincial movement was celebrated as a major achievement serving as a precursor to the creation of Rivers and South Eastern states in 1967.

After this initial breakthrough, many sectional pressure groups manifested to clamour for greater political autonomy for their peoples. Most of these socio-cultural groupings however did not live to see their first or second anniversaries. Later, an all-encompassing movement, the Rivers Chiefs and Peoples' Conference (RCPC), which Professor Atei Okorobia notes emerged to lead the people in the quest for a Rivers State. This account submits it was the RCPC under Chief Dappa Biriye that led the Rivers province to the 1957 London Constitutional Conference to demand for the creation of Rivers state (Okorobia, 2013:95). Arising also from the stiff opposition by the ethnic majors in the regions there arose a wider opinion to extend the state struggle to include other people for wider acceptability from elements both from the Rivers and Calabar Provinces, hence the birth of COR (Calabar, Ogoja, Rivers) state movement. In the Rivers Province Professor Ben Naanen contends the COR state movement derived its main support from certain sections of Degema Division of the Action Group (AG) party. He further stressed that both the Rivers movement and the COR state movement adopted a peaceful constitutional approach featuring petitions, memoranda, lobbying and rallies (Naanen, 2002:342-343).

In the 1957 London Constitutional Conference, the ethnic minorities in the various regions championed the creation of regions or states before the scheduled independence on October 1, 1960. It was decided at the conference due largely to time constraints that the British Government should appoint a commission of inquiry "to ascertain the facts about the fears of minorities in any part of Nigeria and to propose means of allaying those fears whether well or ill founded". On September 25, 1957, James Ojiako writes the British Government appointed Henry Willink's Commission of Inquiry to look into the fears of the minorities (Ojiako, 1981:40). The minorities especially Niger Delta peoples, expectedly, saw this commission as an important opportunity. Though the commission recognized

deeply the concerns and genuineness of the fears of the minorities about their position in the regionalization system. But this enthusiasm was crushed when in its report, the minorities commission decided against the creation of new regions or states on the basis that states would not solve minority problems and that yielding state demands would lead to the disintegration of Nigeria.

The commission, however, recommended a number of palliative measures to allay the fears of the minorities. These measures include among other things the establishment of minority special areas in Benin and Calabar Provinces; the creation of Niger Delta Development Board (NDDDB); the continued implementation of legal reforms to protect non-Muslim minorities in Northern Nigeria; the entrenchment of fundamental human rights in the constitution; the establishment of a national rather than a regionalized police force; and the institutionalization of a plebiscite to determine whether the Ilorin-Kabba Yoruba minority in the North should be transferred to the Western Region (Willink, 1958:58).

It should be emphasized that despite the genuine fears, the commission did not meet the objective needs of the minorities as structurally disadvantaged segments of the Nigerian federation. Accordingly, Nigeria attained independence on October 1, 1960, as a nation state with an unusual composition and weak foundation of legitimacy among the minorities. This defective federal structure Lamy Diamond opines became an important source of the political crisis and ethnic jingoism that convulsed and consumed the first post-independence experiment in democratic governance in Nigeria (Diamond, 1987:209-226)

Even after the attainment of independence in 1960 the dominant political parties were ethnically base rather than rebrand or repackage as national parties. The minority ethnic groups in the regions incessantly complained of victimization and intimidation by the political parties: the Igbo dominated National Council of Nigerian Citizens (NCNC) in the east, the Yoruba dominated Action Group (AG) in the West and Hausa controlled Northern Peoples' Congress (NPC) in the north. Consequently, the minorities greatly resented the control of the regional governments by the majority groups. Conversely, the majority groups too through their regionally controlled parties strongly opposed states creation probably because such exercise, if allowed, would have diminished their bargaining power in the regions.

In their swift reaction the ethnic minorities as a further step founded opposition political parties, cultural associations as well as aligned them with the major parties which supported their cause. Thus, the United Independent party founded by Professor Eyo Ita (in the east), the Middle Belt Congress, the Bornu Youth

Movement (in the north) aligned with the Action Group, the Mid West Democratic Front, the Mid West State Movement, the Benin-Delta Peoples Party (in the west) aligned with the NCNC while the Niger Delta Congress founded by Chief Dappa Biriye (in the east) aligned with the NPC (Bassey, 1980:17; Suberu, 1999:20)

This approach kept ethnic minorities nationalism alive before the coming of military rule in Nigeria, only the Mid-West Region was created by the NPC/NCNC federal coalition government in 1963. The NCNC government headed by Chief Denis Osadebey, an Igbo, was installed in the region (Nwabueze, 1982:151). While not envying the creation of the Mid- Western Region, the action did not reflect the genuine desire of the government to resolve the minorities grievances in Nigeria but was rather self-serving determined to crush the Action Group opposition. The worry is that despite the very restive minorities the federal coalition (NPC/NCNC) parties would not contemplate any re-organization of their respective Northern and Eastern Regional enclaves. Thus, the restructure of the federation into only four regions in 1963 left the lopsided and sick federal structure with destructive ethno-regional conflicts destined the collapse of the first Republic and the imposition of military administration in 1966 (Nwabueze, 1982:148)

Other ethnic minorities in the country had to wait until 1967 when the military administration of Lt. Colonel (later General) Yakubu Gowon broke Nigeria into twelve states. Evidently, Yakubu Gowon's military administration featured among other things, the rise of ethnic minority elements and interests to the fore. Gowon, an army officer from a minority ethnic group, Angas, in the Middle Belt region of Nigeria was conscious of the domineering attitudes of the ethnic majors in the affairs of Nigeria. In an attempt to overcome the teething challenge of the fear of domination by the minority groups was, the substitution of the four region structure with a twelve state system in 1967. Highlighting on the circumstances that shrouded Gowon's most outstanding ethnic balancing or equalization policy as Joseph Elaigwu crafts that he was, from the onset, convinced that "without a definite commitment on the states' question, normalcy and freedom from fear of domination by one region or the other cannot be achieved" (Elaigwu, 1986: 87).

Carefully however, in the wake of threat of the Eastern Region of secession, Gowon on 27 May, 1967, divided the country into twelve states, comprising six states each in the Northern and Southern divide of Nigeria. Scholars have therefore contend that by splitting Northern Nigeria into six states, he did not only gave satisfaction to some primordial Northern minority statehood demands, but also doused Southern apprehensions about the disproportionate size of the North. Perhaps more importantly, the creation of South Eastern and Rivers States for the Niger Delta

ethnic minorities in Eastern Nigeria was decisive in sustaining and maximized their support for the unity of Nigeria (Amuwo et al, 1999:180)

Many other states were created by Gowon's successor military administrations of General Murtala Mohammed in 1976 to nineteen states, twenty one state in 1987 and thirty states in 1991 during General Ibrahim Babangida administration and thirty six states in 1996 during the administration of General Ibrahim Sani Abacha. The major disconnect of the idea of creation of states was essentially to crave for balance and equity but however the exercise gave rise to new majority and new minority within the new states Rivers, for example. Thus, aside conflicts between the major ethnic and minor ethnic groups, there develop conflicts between the new majors and new minorities in Nigeria. Apparently from the foregoing analysis, the issue of creation of states expectedly ensure peace and stability poses elements of threat to Nigeria's unity.

The motive for Gowon's 1967 state creation was to primarily liberate the ethnic minorities from the regional strangle hold of the ethnic majority groups. Conversely, the aim of the 1976 and subsequent state creation exercises was largely one of distributive. Hence, state created after 1967 were expected to serve as avenues for equitable diffusion of the commonwealth of Nigeria rather than being instrument of peace, security and stability. This distributive tendency entailed the balkanization not only of the heterogeneous minority groups but also of the homogeneous majority groups as well. So, it is evidently clear as vividly illustrated in this account that state creation is analogous to the European era of "scramble and partition" by the ethnic majors, using the instrumentality of the apparatus of state powers to grab more revenues in the Nigerian commonwealth or national cake. It is to this controversial issue called revenue allocation/derivation we now turn to quarry in the next segment.

Struggle for Derivation

Since the 1950s, the most controversial issue in horizontal revenue allocation has been derivation. This contentious parlance "derivation" means sharing according to contribution, such that the more one contribute the more one get. Derivation as a concept and a practice has varying meanings and definitions from one scholar to the other. But it means that a certain percentage of the federally collected revenue from each region or state is allocated to that region or state. Stated differently, derivation is a component of fiscal federalism which adheres that a region/state is reallocated a certain percentage from resource tax revenue derived from the exploitation and extraction of natural or created resource in its domain. Accordingly, the rest of the contribution from each of regions/states is paid in a distributive pool account and

the revenue so collected is shared horizontally among the regions/states utilizing other revenue allocation indices like population, need, minimum national standards, and land (Okeke & Omoro, 2015:366-7).

It is arguable to stress that derivation was the most important principle of horizontal revenue allocation from 1954 to 1970. During the period, at least 50% (percent) of the revenue derived from the mineral and agricultural resources of each region was shared on the bases of derivation. Thus, on the basis of the derivation principle, Western Nigeria, the leading cocoa producer, was the fiscally richest region (Okeke, 2019:38). The other two regions, the north was next, and the east last on the fiscal table. During this hibernal times, expectedly, the government of the Eastern Region as Billy Dudley reportedly wrote, strongly contested derivation as a revenue allocation criteria (Dudley, 1973:69-70).

We note however that, the application of the principle of derivation to revenue allocation in Nigeria has after the creation of states in 1967 been subjected to conscious, systematic and unjust manipulations by successive Federal Government, to the detriment of the oil producing minorities. As indicated above, the regions from the 1950s to the time of the twelve state structure in Nigeria retained substantial part of the revenue generated within their domains. The emerging historicity shows that the trend changed as oil found in minority areas emerged as the chief earner of national revenue. The flimflam excuse for the sudden reduction of the weight of derivation was that many new states were not economically viable hence, the federal government began to alter the revenue allocation formula. The financial comatose *abinitio* of many states was blamed on derivation.

Among other measures, the military governments had promulgated four decrees to address the issue of revenue allocation or sharing each which altered the existing basis of revenue allocation. These are Decrees No. 15 of 1967, No. 13 of 1967, No. 9 of 1971 and No. 6 of 1975 (Fayam, 2013:186). The process of reduction and marginalization continued to 1% (one percent) in 1990. Clearly, the ethnic majors were exploiting their hegemony considering the organizational weakness of the oil producing minorities to maximum advantage. Thus, the revenue sharing formula adopted by successive federal governments was termed as one of progressive “rigging of minority economic rights” (The Guardian, 10 May, 1992:23).

It was in this sense of internal colonialism that one source reportedly stated to have bemoan the injustice perpetrated on the Niger Delta peoples thus:

The oil minorities, swathed in deprivation, degradation and unpardonable despoliation, are at the receiving end of deprivation. They are now

protesting to the point of violence against the way that the national revenue is being shared, and are insisting on greater control over the resources in their areas. Virtually all the minority groups are howling that their areas are being deprived of their fair share of national resources, and arguing that the disproportionate advantage enjoyed by the federal government in revenue allocation has created and perpetrated the “dependency syndrome” in state and local governments (News watch, 1990b:40).

Of course, one of the fundamental pillars of federalism is about the sharing of burden and benefit. And the principle suggests that no one group should overstress whatever advantages it has to the detriment of the others. As such, it is essentially to strike a balance between legal justice and social justice. This is understood to mean fairness. It is in this sense of fairness and the give and take context that the need for some kind of financial comparability, and the need for peace, necessitated a downward review of the weight of derivation in the revenue allocation formula. While it was expedient to reduce the weight of derivation resulting from the circumstances that gave birth to it but the extent of its reduction is a matter of concern, not on any objective criteria, but on the relative political strengths of the geo-political regions of the country (Okeke, 2019:40).

One of the reasons the ethnic north gave for fighting to stop the secession of Biafra was to support the Niger Delta minorities’ aspirations of a united Nigeria. According to Dent, Northern blood was shed in the process. For the north, as well as the West, their blood entitled them to a greater share of oil wealth (Dent, 1978). Laughable as the above submission the truth remains that the oil producing minorities states were much smaller in numerical strength and political influence than the non-oil producing states was the reason behind. Besides being relatively small, they were not organizationally strong enough to oppose the federal government. This thought of neo-colonial temper credited to Philip Asiodu, who, though from the minority Delta State, is Igbo by ethnic affiliation, displayed this neo-colonial attitude to the marginalization, deprivation and despoliation of the Niger Delta minorities. He reportedly said that, basically because the peoples of the oil producing areas were minority groups, there would be no serious political issue if derivation were de-emphasized in revenue allocation in the following words:

Given, however, the small size and population of the oil producing areas, it is not cynical to observe that even if the resentments of oil producing states continue, they cannot threaten the stability of the country nor affect its continued economic development (cited in Saro Wiwa, 1989:11-12)

A statement such as the above would underlie the impunity with which the federal governments deals with the revenue allocation saga especially derivation.

However, the ethnic majors, who are, the opponent of derivation did not see anything wrong with reducing its weight from 50% to 1% posited earlier. It is because sharing of the national cake (revenue allocation), has also, for a long time, been tied to the population question. The three most important criteria have been population, equality of states and derivation, but population has jettisoned derivation formula and encouraged marginalization and deprivation of the oil producing minorities from where the bulk of the oil revenue comes. Other allocation principles include land mass, financial comparability, fiscal efficiency internal revenue generation effects, etc. while “water mass” which for obvious reasons, would have favoured the Niger Delta minorities has been completely rejected (Okorobia, 2013:101). The point is that the federal government too had been inconsistent on the revenue allocation issue, since 1947, about twelve (12) commissions/committees came up with their preferences as to how the revenues in the country are to be shared but none is completely accepted by government (Eferebo, 2019:49).

Following political developments in Nigeria during the General Babangida administration’s contentious state of affairs that gave rise to some growing waves of ethnic nationalism among the Niger Delta minorities, for example. The Niger Delta gradually became organizationally more powerful despite its size and population. It engaged in a robust debates and discourses in political and court premises over revenue allocation, allocation of tax powers and expenditure responsibilities with the ethnic jinx breakers of the North and West as well as East, and made their cases or points felt. The Niger Delta minorities especially the Ogoni people brought the matter to global attention through mass protests for justice and the end of marginalization of the area by the Nigerian government. They protested against environmental pollution and destruction of the ecosystem, with Ken Saro Wiwa as lead figure which can be referred to as the contemporary “renaissance” of the Niger Delta minorities nationalism with Movement for the Survival of Ogoni

People (MOSOP) as the instrument tied to non-violent mass movement to register their grievances.

This non-violent mass mobilization and opposition by the minority ethnic groups against what they regard as continued marginalization, exploitation and subjugation in Nigeria by the majority ethnic groups. MOSOP activities became a template to many ethnic organizations especially Ijo National Congress (INC) protested in the oil producing area of the Niger Delta in Nigeria. These peaceful mass protests on many occasions were raided by the police or army involving lots of casualties in the process.

Instructively perhaps from hindsight or probably, in their effort to defend and advance their rights within the Nigerian federation scholars have argued vehemently that, the ethnic minorities especially the Niger Delta in recent time formed or established associations such as the Southern Minorities Forum, the Committee of Oil Producing Areas, the Ijo Ethnic Minority Rights Protection Organization, the Movement for the Survival of Ogoni People (MOSOP), the Movement for Reparation of Oloibiri and so forth (Suberu, 1999:2). These developments among other things culminated to portray the oil producing minorities as a force to be recognized especially for the peace, stability and unity of the Nigerian nation, measures should be taken to eliminate the apparent anathema to national cohesion.

The last decades of the 20th century was the monumental rise of ethnic minorities in the history of Nigeria. There were several launch pads in different quarters, especially the howling of the tremendous wealth that comes from oil channeled to the federal government that has refused to compensate the golden goose that laid the “black gold”. The many demonstrations, protests, strikes, riots and massacres for example shake the very foundations of the nation state, at a time the various segments are in active opposition to one another, and a country so poorly integrated. It is on account of its ‘loose integration’ and oppressive tendency by the ethnic majors on their ethnic minorities as Merton (1968:81) describes Nigeria ‘like a sea anemone’, has several portions of its ‘foot’ clinging tightly to the rock of history, and has suffered ‘serious ruptures’ in its quest to nationhood.

It was these ruptures successive federal governments were to adopt different curative methods, measures and palliatives from NDDB to NDDC agencies, since the first Republic for cure. Despite the palliative cures adopted by governments, the discordant oil producing peoples’ voices of the Niger Delta with regard to derivation as a major criterion in revenue allocation in Nigeria, with every passing year,

became louder and discernible. The minorities in the regions/states were so concerned writes Ugwulor Nwala that:

When the opportunity came in 1994 for another constitutional conference, as part of late General Sani Abacha's transition to civil rule programme, the people agitated and demanded for justice and fair play in allocation of revenue in the country. The 1994 National Constitutional Conference was chaired by a minority, a distinguished legal luminary and Supreme Court Judge, Adolphus Karibi Whyte. There was serious campaign for the purpose and the Niger Delta Forum (NDF) on February 4 – 6, 1994 organized the most successful Pre-Constitutional Conference Workshop in the South – South zone. The workshop was, as expected chaired by Chief Dappa Biriye and issues affecting the minorities were articulated. The Forum then galvanized public opinion and gave direction to the demands of the people of the Niger Delta.

(Nwala, 2003:94)

These and other efforts from several meaningful Nigerians resulted in the entrenchment of 13% (thirteen percent) on the principle of derivation in the (unpublished) 1995 constitution. At the conference, however, delegates from the Southern states campaigned vigorously for state ownership of mineral resources. Despite opposition from the Northern delegates, conference agreed to a significant increase in the weight of derivation, from 1% to 13%. The constitutional proposal was subsequently inculcated in section 162 (2) of the 1999 Constitution.

As a matter of constitutionality after Olusegun Obasanjo became president in 1999, his government did not want to implement the derivation provision in the constitution. In its place, he wanted to establish another federal agency to develop the oil producing minorities. It was named the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC). This generated heated debates in the country. Also, for similar reason the allocation of Revenue Act of 1981 was declared null and void by the Nigerian Supreme Court as a result of law suit that challenged its constitutionality. The former Bendel State Government instituted the suit against the Attorney General of the Federation and others. Apparently, the suit arose out of perceived manipulation of the allocation formula in favour of the Federal Government and the neglect of derivation principle (Nwala, 2003:92).

In the Obasanjo era too the issue also raised lots of dust as the oil producing areas of the Niger Delta labelled the federal government as being autocratic and insensitive about the sensibilities of the plight of the minorities. As a backlash the Federal Government introduced the on-shore/off-shore dichotomy implying that oil found in the sea cannot be ascribed to the adjoining state. The on-shore/off-shore controversy resulted in states of the Niger Delta region calling for a greater control of their resources (petroleum and gas). Expectedly, this eventually culminated to the struggle for resource control which climaxed by some states suing the Federal Government terminating in the Supreme Court that ruled in favour of the 13% derivation in April 2002 (Ukuta, 2009:98).

Arguably, despite the Supreme Court interpretation of the constitutionality of the principle of derivation in the country has not laid the years of oil producing Niger Delta minorities marginalization and deprivation to rest, as posited elsewhere in this paper. This was graphically demonstrated during the discussions and submissions of the South-South delegates at the National Conference in 2014 tends to show like “Oliver Twist” demanded a 25% increase in derivation. It is therefore crystal clear from this submission which corroborates the fact that the derivation struggle and debates would continue into an unforeseeable future in the country.

Armed Struggle

Interestingly, the history of the Niger Delta peoples before colonial times is replete with attempts by people external to the region to sequester the resources of their peoples. It is in the defense of their people and resources that made heroes of the likes of Jaja of Opobo, William Frederick Koko of Nembe, Nana Olomu of Itsekiri just to mention a few of the leaders. The point has to be made that the reckless exploitation of oil and gas resources of the region by the Nigerian state and its collaborator agencies, the multi-national oil corporations drew a serious reaction or backlash from a people who have a long history of resistance against any form of oppression (Eferebo & Eweke, 2018:5).

The point was further stressed that there have always been complaints of neglect and marginalization of infrastructure in the Niger Delta even at the height of colonial rule. It is in calling attention to this infrastructural challenge that they were blackmailed with names. The region suffered considerable neglect from the colonial government with the pretext that not much revenue was generated from the region to justify the weighty capital necessary to provide for the infrastructural deficit. The establishment of the minorities commission of inquiry in 1957 and its subsequent report was the culmination of a groundswell of discontent that was not adequately

addressed (Ogbogbo, 2018:13). Convinced however, that the Niger Delta was and is actually “poor, backward and neglected”, became a fertile ground for conflict. It is against this drawback that the area has inadvertently become a place of frustrated expectations, with a siege mentality, especially among the army of unemployed youths who are dejected to a future without aspirations. As a viable consequence to the general marginalization, neglect and environmental degradation, the youths adopted confrontational strategies to redress the challenge. The deplorable neglect of the region is vividly captured by Isaac Boro in his book, the Twelve Day Revolution, in which he posited that:

First, we may run our eyes through the health services of the area concerned, covering a territory of 10,000 square miles and about two million inhabitants there are just a few hospitals of ordinary health centre status. One is at Degema, the second at Yenagoa and the other at Okrika. It takes about two days to travel by canoe from most of the remote villages to any of the hospitals ...

Continuing further he wrote that:

There are few dispensaries not better than first aid boxes scattered about in some of the villages. There are no maternity homes. How do people in such an environment survive? No wonder the high death rate. The survivors of these horrid conditions live ... on herbs (Boro, 1982:64).

Due largely to the issues substantiated above, Isaac Boro launched the campaign with his compatriots Samuel Owonaro and Nottingham Dick and others organized the Niger Delta Volunteer Service (NDVS) and declare the Niger Delta Peoples' Republic. Essentially for the Niger Delta people to control the oil and gas resources in their domain (resource control) for developmental reasons. However, the twelve days old republic was crushed, but it brought consciousness to the people. This action was not wanting destruction but a war of liberation from the regional and federal governments that were daft to the plight of the Niger Delta oil producing minorities. Given the predatory character of the Nigerian state since independence, the oil producing minorities have remain voiceless and largely oppressed and marginalized. The implication is that their agitations are not taken into account by the rapacious ruling class, until the dawn of democratic rule in 1999.

Following the non-violent option undertaken by the environmental activist, the late Kenule Saro-Wiwa in the last decade of the twentieth century through the platform

of MOSOP, which was founded in 1992. The implication of the non-violent approach of Saro-Wiwa can only be appreciated by hindsight because we can start something one day, but we may not know when the process will end. Even within the community, there are variance of agitations and aspirations begging to be actualized as is the case of Nigeria where the oil producing Niger Delta minorities are begging for justice, fairness and equity which Saro-Wiwa and his MOSOP represents as we have established elsewhere.

However and very importantly, that every legitimate struggle especially the Niger Delta oil producing minorities would sure get actualized but we can never be so sure when exactly or at what stage would it get materialized. While some of the struggles may get actualized, readily soon, faster than we had ever anticipated. This could be true in the case of Dr. Goodluck Jonathan, from the South-South geopolitical zone who became Vice President and later Nigeria's substantive President in a single stroke in 2010, at an historic stage when Nigerians least expected for example. Similarly, some of the struggles may have to wait for decades and even more before they could be actualized as is the case of the derivation principle as the basis of revenue allocation in Nigeria.

This was probably the historical lens through which the environmental activist, Kenule Saro-Wiwa saw the Niger Delta struggle, and he thus, joined other world peace advocates like Mahatma Gandhi and Martin Luther King Jr as Michael Jayeoba situates this priceless enterprise thus:

Preached to support the idea of non-violence approach to civil agitations, perhaps to ensure that agitations would not lose focus and in the process destroy the future of the society for which they profess love, demanding for positive changes. This is to point out that since we are fully aware that societal agitations, aspirations and hopes can never be actualized, all at a time, champions of societal agitations *“especially the oil producing Niger Delta minorities”* at a particular time frame should strive to achieve through peaceful means, positive changes as ably possible but should endeavour to put in place appropriate mechanism to pass on the struggle for positive change to upcoming generations for further successes (Jayeoba, 2011:27, *my italics*).

This was the prophetic slogan of Saro-Wiwa and what MOSOP stood for in the Niger Delta struggle before the four Ogoni chiefs were murdered and their death

was, without evidence, attributed to the leadership of MOSOP. In view of the fact that their agitations was hitting hard on the economy, and the integrity and credibility of the leadership of the country, Saro-Wiwa and eight other Ogoni members of the MOSOP were arrested, tried and killed on December 10, 1995, as a way of removing those people agitating for justice and equity in the country. Professor Emordi however notes that, the result was the further militarization of the region, and it was the propelling factor that snowballed to the Kaiama Declaration in later years (Emordi, 2019:24).

After the death of Kenule Saro-Wiwa and the Ogoni eight chiefs, the struggle moved to a level of militancy, which assumed a deadlier and more dangerous dimension with consequences that became global in nature. Arising from the predatory attitude of the Federal Government, it became crystal clear that the non-violent approach cannot compel the Nigerian state and its partners in the crime, the multinational oil companies to address the burning issues of environmental degradation, wide spread poverty and general underdevelopment of the Niger Delta. Of importance, following the December 11, 1998 Kaiama Declaration, which was wholly represented the various Ijo clans and organizations well attended to discuss the way forward of their continued survival in the Nigerian state.

As a consequence of the declaration, the youths took to the creeks and constituted themselves into armed militia forces against the federal government in the guise of agitation of resource control. The regimented formations include, Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Young Shall Grow (YSG), Niger Delta People Volunteer Force (NDPVF), Movement for the Survival of the Ijo Ethnic Nationality (MOSIEN), the Joint Revolutionary Council (JRC), among several other militia groups. Accordingly, they armed themselves with all kinds of assorted weapons ready for a showdown with government and its security outfits in the country. The militants adopted guerrilla strategies of confrontation, seizure and destruction of oil exploiting facilities, kidnapping of oil workers and attacking fortified military formations, and this continued until the regime of President Umaru Yar'Adua, who granted the militant amnesty under the conditions that they surrender their arms to the government.

It is therefore, essential to interrogate the circumstances which brought the change from non-violence to one of armed confrontation in the Niger Delta struggle? The Niger Delta struggle is a historical process born out of the history of Nigeria, and the subsequent subjugation, and marginalization, discrimination and oppression in their fatherland. And, as a process, sometimes non-violent and at other times violent, slow and fast, debates in conferences and parliaments takes care of the web that

needed the machine of history to quarry. We note however, three factors appeared to have been responsible for this transformation from Saro-Wiwa non-violent agitation to militancy in the region. Some sources however adduce that:

The first, of course, is the gruesome murder of Saro-Wiwa and eight of his ethnic members; the second was the arming of youths for misuse as thugs by political office holders in the region beginning from the 1999 general elections; and the third was the mass mobilization to Abuja of youths from all over Nigeria by a one-time head of state, General Sani Abacha, as rented crowd in solidarity with his ambition to transform into a civilian president. During their brief sojourn in Abuja, the Niger Delta Youths are said to have seen, for the first time, the great new city that was the Federal capital, which was built by oil money that flowed from their impoverished and neglected region (Imbua et al, 2017:258-259).

They further articulates the combination of the three factors that possibly launch the youths of the region into militancy that became a real threat to the unity, peace, security and survival of the nation, and which disrupted the Nigeria oil production and global oil prices intermittently.

By and large, these Niger Delta militants turned out to betray the “body and soul” of the peoples’ aspiration for their selfish gains as they were allegedly “settled” by the government of the day, themselves indigene of the region, who is reported to have awarded them contracts in billions of naira to “protect” oil installations in the region. It is worrisome that, “the decent and patriotic struggle for the survival of the people and their environment for which Isaac Adaka Boro and Kenule Saro-Wiwa fought (both killed in the struggle), was transformed into the personal wealth of the current generation of agitators. Unfortunately, theirs’ is the story of the Nigerian military Professor Emordi called “maidguard” employed by a family becomes the head of the family he is employed to guard; as he becomes the thief he is employed to catch, in that case nothing is safe and secured in that house (Emordi 2019:7). Similarly it is the case of self-appointed watchmen over a community’s treasure but who have, themselves, becomes the thieves in the same treasury according to the account, completely looting the poor community of both the treasure and the services of other potential watchmen (Imbua et al, 2017:259) is analogous to the Niger Delta struggle

The point been made is that like every other struggle there are bound to be confluences and crosscurrents that essentially keeps the struggle alive the ideals for future generations. And like a chain, the struggle continues until justice, fairness and equity is assured of minorities' rights especially those of the Niger Delta of Nigeria. It is seen like a rally race from Chief Biriye, Isaac Boro, Kenule Saro-Wiwa among other notable leaders, who passed the batten to the present agitators which they would in turn pass the struggle over to future generations for further success. In the present however, they did not achieve resource control, but got other concessions, namely a political compromise of the onshore/offshore controversy, the amnesty programme, the NDDC, the establishment of the Ministry of Niger Delta, and above all, the Office of the president Federal Republic of Nigeria.

Concluding Comments

This paper has interrogated the phenomenon of ethnic minorities' nationalism in Nigeria especially the Niger Delta peoples as its main focus. The point made is that political and socio-economic discrimination, marginalization, frustration and domination under the tripartite regional system in the colonial and early post-independence eras gave rise to the minorities' agitations for the creation of states or regions in which the minorities' problem would be significantly ameliorated or if not completely eliminated. But, in spite of the minorities' genuine fear of domination by the ethnic majors of Hausa, Yoruba and Igbo the demands for regions/states creation were been frustrated by the colonial administration. And therefore, state creation in Nigeria, became a post-independence development carried out mostly by the military administrations with the exception of the creation of the Mid-Western Region in 1963. The paper however established that revenue allocation formula adopted by the successive federal government was one of progressive rigging of minority economic rights through the massive transfer of wealth from the oil producing communities of the Niger Delta to other parts of Nigeria especially the majority groups' areas. Thus, it is in calling attention to this deliberate neglect, poverty, hopelessness and infrastructural challenge that occasioned the armed confrontation by the Niger Delta peoples with its code name militancy as backlash against the federal government and its agents; with a view to control resources in their domain for the reduction of the weight of derivation as the criterion for revenue allocation in the country.

It is therefore pertinent to say that, the problems of the minorities especially the oil producing communities of the Niger Delta in Nigeria is likely to continue ad infinitum unless measures are taken to give them equal opportunities with the majority groups in the country.

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